

This identity of teresantalene with tricyclene has been established by Ruzicka and Liebel (*loc. cit.*) by converting (IV) into the corresponding aldehyde, teresantalal (VII), the semicarbazone of which on treatment with sodium ethylate gave tricyclene. The synthesis of the hydrocarbon tricyclene by oxidising camphor-hydrazone with mercuric oxide in alkaline solution (Meerwein and Emster, *loc. cit.*) leaves no doubt about the correctness of the structure (VI). It is therefore evident that *tricycloekasantalic acid* (I) and its degradation products are derivatives of tricyclene (VI) and as such are related to π -derivatives of camphor (*vide formula*). It appeared to us feasible to synthesise *tricycloekasantalic acid* (I) and its products of degradation from suitable π -derivatives of camphor. (*cf.* however, Asahina, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 76; 1935, 68, 952; Sahasi and Iki, *Sci. papers Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Japan*, 1934, 25, 48, 73).

Taking camphor as our starting material, it has been possible to synthesise (I) by passing through the syntheses of π -hydroxycamphor, teresantalol (IV) and teresantaly chloride (V). *d*- π -Bromocamphor, which was the essential material for this investigation, was prepared from camphor according to the method of Pope and Kipping (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 553; 1895, 65, 357) with some modifications.

d-Camphor was brominated to *d*- α -bromocamphor (VIII), which on sulphonation either with fuming sulphuric acid or chlorosulphonic acid, furnished the corresponding π -sulphonic acid (IX). The ammonium salt of (IX) was converted by phosphorus pentabromide into the corresponding sulphonyl bromide (X) which on being heated above its melting point was converted almost quantitatively into *d*- α - π -dibromocamphor (XI) with the elimination of sulphur dioxide. Dibromocamphor (XI) on reduction with zinc and acetic acid was converted into *d*- π -bromocamphor (XII); only the α -bromine atom being replaced by hydrogen. The compound (XII) was also prepared by first reducing the ammonium salt of (IX) with zinc dust and ammonia to the ammonium salt of *d*-camphor- π -sulphonic acid (XIII). This in its turn was converted into the corresponding sulphonyl bromide (XV) which on heating above its melting point furnished (XII). (See page. 273).

Both the methods for the preparation of compound (XII) were found to be equally satisfactory but in the former process a little caution was necessary during the reduction of (XI), as otherwise the reaction is attended with the formation of some non-halogenated products.

Unsubstituted *d*- and *dl*-camphor on sulphonation produced inactive camphor- π -sulphonic acid, the active camphor being racemised, during sulphonation. This inactive sulphonic acid was converted into *dl*- π -bromocamphor exactly according to the process mentioned previously. It has, however, been observed that the yield of reaction products obtained with the inactive compounds gets always very much diminished in quantity. Equally unsatisfactory results were obtained when chlorine was used in place of bromine and phosphorus pentachloride in place of pentabromide.

The bromine atom of *d*- π -bromo-camphor (XII), as is evident from its method of preparation by the reduction of (XI), is comparatively inert. It cannot be

hydrolysed even by 30% alcoholic alkali under pressure and it does not react with magnesium in ethyl or amyl ether to produce the corresponding Grignard compound. It does not react with potassium or sodium derivative of ethyl malonate. This peculiar inertness of the π -bromine atom does not seem to have been thoroughly examined by earlier workers. It is, however, well known (Kipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 913, 928) that when the π -bromocamphor is oxidised to bromocamphoric acid, the inertness of the bromine atom in the latter completely disappears. It is clear therefore that the inertness of the bromine atom in π -bromocamphor is due to the steric influence exerted by the bicyclic structure.

As it appears to be the easiest process, an attempt has been made to prepare teresantyl bromide directly from (XII) by converting it into the corresponding hydrazone and subsequently oxidising the latter in the usual way with yellow oxide of mercury. But instead of the desired product, a mixture containing traces of a compound which from its melting point appears to be teresantalol, tricyclene and an azo compound are obtained. The following method has been adopted for the preparation of teresantalol and its derivatives.

The compound (XII) is boiled with potassium acetate and glacial acetic acid, and thus converted into an acetoxy derivative (XVI) which on hydrolysis furnishes *d*- π -hydroxycamphor (XVII). The hydrazone (XVIII) of this hydroxy-ketone (XVII) on oxidation with mercuric oxide in alkaline solution produces *d*-teresantalol (IV). The action of hydrazine hydrate (50%) in alcoholic solution on camphor and π -hydroxycamphor is very slow, about 170 hours being necessary for the completion of the reaction. The same reaction, however, is completed within 12 hours when camphor or π -hydroxycamphor is slowly refluxed with 100% hydrazine hydrate.

The hydroxyl group in teresantalol (IV) is also comparatively inert. On treatment with excess of thionyl chloride in pyridine solution it gives a poor yield of teresantyl chloride. Impure teresantyl chloride has been prepared by the action of phosphorus pentachloride on teresantalol (IV) in low boiling petrol. It is a well known fact that cyclopropane ring is vulnerable to the action of phosphorus

pentahalides and in fact all reagents which produce hydrogen halides attack a *cyclo*-propane ring with the production of chlorinated bicyclic decomposition products. It is because of this reason that Semmler's teresantalane (VI) could not be identified with tricyclene. Teresantaly chloride, which has been used for this purpose, is prepared by the action of phosphorus pentachloride on the corresponding alcohol teresantalol, during which operation some chlorinated bicyclic decomposition products are formed, which appear to have been responsible for Semmler's difficulty in identifying teresantalane with tricyclene.

Similar difficulties are encountered in the thujane series (Semmler, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3345; Kondakov, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1900, *ii*, 62, 176) *viz.* in the preparation of thujyl chloride by the action of phosphorus pentachloride on thujyl alcohol, when besides the partial formation of thujyl chloride, there are also formed some impure products by the rupture of the *cyclo*propane ring.

The halogen atom in teresantaly chloride (V) is inert and does not react with sodium derivative of malonic ester in either benzene or alcoholic solution. It is condensed with potassium derivative of ethyl malonate in xylene suspension under pressure with the formation of impure teresantaly malonic ester (XIX). The free malonic acid derivative separates in an oily form and could not be crystallised, and eliminates carbon dioxide on heating. From the residual oil *tricyclo*-ekasantalic acid (I) could be isolated by steam distillation. The yield is only about 3% of the theoretical amount.

*Tricyclo*ekasantalic acid, thus prepared, has a feeble *dextro*-rotation showing that partial racemisation has taken place during the course of reaction. The success of this experiment depends entirely on the successful preparation of teresantaly chloride (V) in which operation the treatment with phosphorus pentachloride should not be allowed to be too drastic.

The corresponding inactive compounds of the series could be prepared in an exactly analogous manner from inactive π -bromocamphor.

EXPERIMENTAL

d- α -Bromocamphor was obtained by directly brominating *d*-camphor according to the method of Armstrong (*Chem. News*, 1878, 37, 4); camphor (152 g.) gave α -bromocamphor (190-200 g.), m.p. 76°; $[\alpha]_D = +140$.

Sulphonation of α -bromo camphor was carried out according to the following three processes using

- (i) chlorosulphonic acid in chloroform solution, (Pope and Kipping, *loc. cit.*),
- (ii) chlorosulphonic acid but without any solvent,
- (iii) fuming sulphuric acid of a particular concentration.

All the processes were found to be satisfactory, but the second one was the most convenient. In this process (i) almost 50% of chloroform used (about 133 c.c. for 100 g. of bromocamphor) is lost and sulphonation also takes about 12 hours for completion. In process (iii) a huge amount of calcium sulphate requires to be dealt with, whereas in method (ii) no such difficulties are encountered. The process is described below :

d- α -Bromocamphor (100 g.) was placed in a round-bottom flask fitted with a long condenser, a dropping funnel and calcium chloride guard tube. Chlorosulphonic acid (75 c.c.) was then added in three instalments at intervals of 5 minutes under shaking. The flask was then warmed to 60°-70° on a water-bath for about 30 minutes until a sample of the reaction mixture dissolved completely in water. The brownish viscous mass was neutralised by sufficient amount of calcium carbonate suspended in water. The precipitated calcium sulphate was filtered off and washed thoroughly with water. To the hot filtrate the requisite amount of ammonium carbonate was added and the precipitated calcium carbonate was filtered off and washed. The solution of the ammonium salt on evaporation and cooling deposited crystals of ammonium *d*- α -bromocamphor- π -sulphonate, which after filtration and washing with 95% alcohol, gave beautiful colourless crystals, yield 90-100 g.

Ammonium salt of d-Camphor- π -sulphonic Acid.—*d*-Ammonium α -bromocamphor- π -sulphonate (250 g.) was dissolved in 10% ammonia solution (1000 c.c.) and zinc dust (100 g.) added gradually during 20 minutes, there being a considerable rise of temperature in the beginning. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for 40 minutes, and the residual zinc dust filtered off. The hot filtrate was saturated with hydrogen sulphide and the precipitated zinc sulphide removed by filtration. The filtrate containing ammonium salt of *d*-camphor- π -sulphonic acid and ammonium bromide in equivalent proportion was evaporated nearly to dryness and allowed to cool. The crystals obtained were further purified by washing successively with alcohol and ether. The yield of the ammonium salt and ammonium bromide was 265 g.

d- α -Bromocamphor- π -sulphonyl Bromide.—Dry ammonium *d*- α -bromocamphor- π -sulphonate (60 g.) was treated with phosphorus pentabromide (85 g.) in the usual way (Pope and Kipping, *loc. cit.*) and the crude sulphonyl bromide crystallised from ethyl acetate, yield 35 g., softens at 137° and melts completely at 145°; $[\alpha]_D$ in chloroform solution, +144.9°.

d- α - π -Dibromocamphor.—*d*- α -Bromocamphor- π -sulphonyl bromide (100 g.), taken in a 500 c.c. beaker and covered with a clock glass, was heated in a metal-bath. Decomposition commenced at 150°, the temperature was gradually raised to 160-170°

and kept there for about 10 minutes during which the evolution of sulphur dioxide was complete. The molten mass after cooling was dissolved in hot acetic acid containing a little nitric acid from which on cooling *d-a- π* -dibromocamphor precipitated. The substance was recrystallised from alcohol, yield 77 g., m.p. 152°; $[\alpha]_D$, +98.99° (in chloroform solution).

d- π -Bromocamphor.—*d-a- π* -Dibromocamphor (47 g.) was dissolved in sufficient amount of 80% hot acetic acid and zinc dust (20 g.) was added during 10 minutes, care being taken that the reaction was neither too vigorous nor too sluggish. After the reaction subsided, the solution was filtered while hot and the residue on filter paper washed with hot acetic acid. The filtrate was cooled, diluted with a sufficient amount of cold water and allowed to stand overnight. The precipitated *d- π* -bromocamphor was filtered off, dried and crystallised from low boiling petrol, yield 34 g., m.p. 94°; $[\alpha]_D$, 121.3° (in chloroform solution).

d-Camphor- π -sulphonyl Bromide.—Ammonium *d*-camphor- π -sulphonate (60 g.) was treated with phosphorus pentabromide in the usual way (Pope and Kipping, *loc. cit.*), the crude sulphonyl bromide was crystallised from ethyl acetate, yield 60-70%, m.p. 145°; $[\alpha]_D$, +147.2°.

Decomposition of d-camphor- π -sulphonyl Bromide to d- π -Bromocamphor.—*d*-Camphor-sulphonyl bromide (100 g.) was decomposed exactly as in the case of *d-a*-bromocamphor- π -sulphonyl bromide but at a temperature of 150-160°. *d- π* -Bromocamphor crystallised from petrol-ether, yield 75 g., m.p. 94°; $[\alpha]_D$, +121.9°.

Two methods of preparing *d- π* -bromocamphor have been described above: (i) by the reduction of *d-a- π* -dibromocamphor, (ii) by the decomposition of *d- π* -sulphonyl bromide.

Both the methods are equally satisfactory. But in method (i) some careful control of the reduction is necessary, otherwise some non-halogenated products are formed. Of course, if carefully performed, it gives a very satisfactory yield of *d- π* -bromocamphor. The method (ii) is free from all uncertain factors and is the surer of the above two methods.

dl- π -Bromocamphor was obtained in an analogous manner from *dl- π* -sulphonic acid which was obtained by the direct sulphonation of unsubstituted camphor with chlorosulphonic acid. The impure ammonium salt which could not be crystallised gave a 25% yield of *dl- π* -sulphonyl bromide (m.p. 125-30°), which on subsequent decomposition above its melting point gave a nearly theoretical yield of *dl- π* -bromocamphor, m.p. 93.5°.

d- π -Acetoxycamphor.—*d- π* -Bromocamphor (50 g.), anhydrous potassium acetate (100 g.), and glacial acetic acid (100 g.) were slowly refluxed in an oil-bath (170-180°) for 24 hours. The product was poured into cold water, neutralised with soda and extracted with ether. The dry ethereal solution on evaporation and subsequent

distillation in vacuum gave *d*- π -acetoxycamphor, b.p. 123°/5 mm., yield 38.3 g. (Found : C, 67.1 ; H, 8.81. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.57 ; H, 8.6 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 234°. (Found : C, 57.90 ; H, 7.72 ; N, 16.01. $C_{13}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 58.42 ; H, 7.90 ; N, 15.73 per cent).

d- π -*Hydroxycamphor*.—Acetoxycamphor (38.3 g.) was dissolved in 10% alcoholic potash solution (400 c.c.) and boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After distilling off the excess of alcohol, the residue was poured into cold water, saturated with common salt and extracted with ether. The residue left after distillation of ether was crystallised from a mixture of petrol and benzene ; yield 29.1 g., m. p. 234° ; $[\alpha]_D$, 63.6. (Found : C, 71.7 ; H, 9.82. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.47 ; H, 9.52 per cent).

dl- π -*Hydroxycamphor* was prepared in an exactly analogous way from *dl*- π -bromocamphor, which was at first converted into the acetoxy derivative (b.p. 123°/4 mm.) and then by hydrolysis to *dl*- π -hydroxycamphor ; yield same as in the previous case, m.p. 233°. (Found : C, 71.29. H, 9.92. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.47 ; H, 9.59 per cent).

It may be interesting to note that both *d*- and *dl*- π -hydroxycamphor did not form any semicarbazone in the usual way, but they gave hydrazones on treatment with hydrazine hydrate.

d-*Teresantalol*.—*d*- π -Hydroxycamphor (27 g.), and 100% hydrazine hydrate (10 g.) were dissolved in 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol and refluxed in a three-necked flask for 150-170 hours and thus converted into the hydrazone, (the same reaction may also be successfully performed by refluxing slowly a mixture of the hydroxy ketone, with 100% hydrate for 10-15 hours), which without being isolated was utilised for the subsequent reaction. To this mixture potassium hydroxide (4 g.), dissolved in 10 c.c. of water, and diluted with 50 c.c. of alcohol, was added and the mixture stirred mechanically. Freshly prepared yellow oxide of mercury (50 g.) was then gradually added during 10 minutes, brisk evolution of nitrogen taking place throughout the course of addition. Stirring was continued for another 24 hours, after which the mercuric slime was filtered off. The residual oil left after removal of alcohol was distilled in vacuum ; teresantalol distilled at about 90°/5 mm. and solidified inside the condenser. It was recrystallised from a mixture of petrol-ether and benzene, yield 13 g., m.p. 115° ; $[\alpha]_D$, +121° ; natural variety, m.p. 114° ; $[\alpha]_D$, 11.58. (Found : C, 79.1 ; H, 10.68. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.9 ; H, 10.4 per cent).

Teresantalol is extremely volatile and great care should be taken during its distillation.

dl-*Teresantalol* was prepared in an analogous way from *dl*- π -hydroxycamphor, m.p. 117°. (Found : C, 79.0 ; H, 10.71. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.7 ; H, 10.6 per cent).

d-*Teresantalyl Chloride*.—*d*-Teresantalol (30 g.) was covered with a few c.c. of petrol-ether and phosphorus pentachloride ($1\frac{1}{2}$ mol.) was added gradually. The

mixture was triturated for about 20 minutes and left aside for 5-10 minutes and then poured into ice-water, extracted with ether, washed with cold water and distilled in vacuum. Teresantalyl chloride distilled at 77-87°/9 mm. The substance emitted an acrid smell.

d-Teresantalylmalonic Ester.—Clean potassium (78 g.; 2 mol.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (200 c. c.) contained in a three-necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a guard tube. Malonic ester (32 g.) was then added and the mixture heated on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Alcohol was then completely removed at 120-140° under reduced pressure and sodium-dried xylene (180 c. c.) containing teresantalyl chloride (17.1 g.) was poured in. The mixture was transferred to a soda-water bottle and heated under pressure at 170-190° for 30 hours. From the filtered solution xylene was removed by distillation under diminished pressure and the residue was distilled under vacuum. Teresantalylmalonic ester came over at 130-145°/13 mm., yield 8 g.

As envisaged by subsequent investigation, only a minor portion of the distillate was teresantalylmalonic ester, the rest being other impurities.

Teresantalyl chloride, used by us, was impure and contained some acidic impurities; when the above reaction was done in alcoholic solution under ordinary pressure nearly one atomic proportion of sodium or potassium was neutralised and alkali halides separated easily. From the reaction mixture free malonic ester could be detected, but no teresantalylmalonic ester was formed. Similar results were obtained in benzene suspension. Expected result could only be obtained in xylene suspension under pressure and using an excess of potassium. Teresantalyl chloride used in this reaction should be freshly prepared.

d-Tricycloekasantalic Acid.—Impure teresantalyl malonic ester, as obtained above, was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash (10%) and then just acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. From the ethereal extract, teresantalylmalonic acid could not be crystallised. The impure oily liquid was heated in an oil-bath at 180-200°, when carbon dioxide began to evolve. After the evolution of carbon dioxide had ceased, the viscous mass was subjected to steam distillation. *d-Tricycloekasantalic acid* came over with steam as a semi-solid mass and was recrystallised from alcohol and then from low boiling petrol; yield 0.9 g. (3-4% of theory); m. p. 76°; $[\alpha]_{5780} +1.0$ to $+3.1^{\circ}$; variety from natural source, m. p. 76.4°; $[\alpha]_{5780} +15.4^{\circ}$.

Equivalent weight was determined by titration in alcoholic solution with standard alkali using phenolphthalein as indicator (Found: C, 74.61; H, 9.30. Equiv. 191.1. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 74.19; H, 9.33 per cent. Equiv. 192.25).

The Methyl ester was prepared from the silver salt and alkyl iodide, b. p. 127°/10 mm.; d_4^{20} , 1.0165; n_D^{20} , 1.4782. (Found: C, 74.71; H, 9.61. $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 74.95; H, 9.3 per cent).

dl-*Tricycloekasantalic acid* was prepared in an analogous way. Crystallisation in this case was comparatively difficult and the yield was even poorer; m.p. 75°: Equiv. wt. 194.2. (Found: C, 73.99; H, 9.60. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 74.19; H, 9.33 per cent). Methyl ester, b. p. 127°/10 mm; n_D^{20} , 1.4783 (Found: C, 74.3; H, 10.1. $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 74.3; H, 10.5 per cent).

Further work for the preparation of optically pure *tricycloekasantalic acid* by a different method is in progress.

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STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART III. SYNTHESES OF *d*- α -SANTALAL AND *d*- α -SANTALOL

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The aldehyde *tricycloekasantal* has been condensed with propionic aldehyde in presence of alcoholic alkali to produce *d*-santalal. Santalal has been reduced with aluminium ethoxide to *d*- α -santalol, identical with the natural product.

In Part II of this series, the syntheses of some of the degradation products of *d*- α -santalol has been dealt with. In this part, the syntheses of the parent substance *d*- α -santalol, as also of the corresponding aldehyde *d*- α -santalal has been described. Semmier made a very exhaustive study of the chemistry of the degradation products of α -santalol and ascribed to it ($C_{15}H_{24}O$) the structure (I).

According to him, α -santalol (I) is a tricyclic primary alcohol with a long side-chain possessing an ethylenic linkage. When *d*- α -santalol (I) is oxidised with chromic